

THE POSSIBLE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION ON 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ERA

Doris Chasokela^{1*}, Alfred Henry Makura²

¹Ms., Central University of Technology, SOUTH AFRICA, doris.chasokela@nust.ac.zw

² Prof., Central University of Technology, SOUTH AFRICA,

*Corresponding author

Abstract

This paper examines the possible impact of technology integration on 21st-century skills in Zimbabwe during the COVID-19 pandemic at a STEM university in Zimbabwe. A qualitative approach was used and the population comprises lecturers, technicians, and students in a university with seven faculties. Two lecturers from each faculty were selected. Focus group from each faculty had five students and one technician was sampled also from each faculty. Interviews and focus group discussions were used to collect data. The data was analysed thematically with an element of voice from the respondents. The university is using Google Classroom and partly Moodle. The findings suggest that the use of technology during the pandemic had a positive impact on student's critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills. However, there were challenges in the implementation of technology, including a lack of internet access and technical difficulties. It is therefore recommended that the government and other stakeholders provide adequate resources and training to teachers in order to effectively implement technology integration. The findings from interviews found that, overall; students felt that technology integration had a positive impact on their 21st-century skills. The students reported that they had gained skills in problem-solving, critical thinking, and digital literacy. The interviews with lecturers revealed that the use of technology had helped to improve student engagement, collaboration, and communication. It is therefore recommended that the government and other stakeholders increase investment in technology infrastructure. Also to develop blended learning models that combine online and face-to-face instruction, and provide the necessary support for lecturers and students. Evaluate and monitor the implementation of technology integration initiatives to ensure that they are effective and meet the needs of students.

Keywords: Technology integration, 21st-century skills, Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), problem-based learning, Higher Education

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on education around the world. Universities have been forced to switch to online and distance learning, with many students learning from home. This has presented both challenges and opportunities for lecturers and students. While there is some evidence that online learning can be effective, there is also concern about the quality of instruction and the impact on student learning. This study focuses on the experience of STEM students in universities in Zimbabwe and

investigates the impact of technology integration on their 21st-century skills.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition (SAMR) model. The SAMR model provides a framework for evaluating the impact of technology integration, with higher levels of integration leading to a greater impact on student learning. This model is used to guide the research design and analysis of the data collected. SAMR model improves the critical thinking of the students as they integrate technology (Crompton & Burke 2020). SAMR is significant in the understanding and integration of technology (Hamilton Rosenberg & Akcaoglu 2016; Bicalho, Coll, Engel & Lopes de Oliveira 2023).

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Impact of technology integration on 21st-century skills among STEM students during the COVID-19 pandemic

This study reviews the literature on technology integration and 21st-century skills to identify the current state of research and gaps in knowledge. The study found that most of the research focuses on the impact of technology on specific 21st-century skills, such as problem-solving and critical thinking, rather than the broader set of skills (Gosnell 2023; Kucuk 2023; Phillips 2023; Ratotti 2023). Most lecturers and students in Zimbabwe are facing the challenge of integrating 21st-century skills (Moyo & Hadebe 2018). Technology integration has room to increase student engagement and satisfaction as they explore (Al Yakin & Seraj 2023; Hanaysha, Shriedeh & In'airat 2023; Hazzam & Wilkins 2023; Pandita & Kiran 2023; Tawafak, Al-Obaydi, Klimova & Pikhart 2023). According to Wilson (2023) and Nunez (2023), best teaching practices are promoted through hands-on experiences in technology integration. Technology integration prepares future lecturers and students for healthy pedagogical uses of technology and knowledge creation (Abedi, Prestridge & Hodge 2023; Wilson 2023). Mondal (2021); Howcroft & Taylor (2023) posit that technology integration increases the permanence of knowledge and its greater understanding. According to Kucuk (2023) and Baas et al. (2023), obtaining data and resources in a short period of time as technology is integrated and ease of collaboration. Additionally, technology has an impact on the job market as technology is evolving rapidly therefore there is a need to keep abreast with it (Farsawang & Songkram 2023; Vapiwala, Pandita & Choudhury 2023).

3.2 Challenges and opportunities associated with technology integration in STEM education during the pandemic

This study reviews the literature on the challenges and opportunities associated with distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Technology infrastructure, lecturer preparedness, and access to resources are key challenges to technology integration (Kihzoza et al. 2016; Mpofu & Mpofu 2023; Williams et al. 2023). Several researchers share the same sentiment that infrastructure in technology integration is a critical challenge (Nikou & Maslov 2023; Timotheou et al. 2023; Wohlfart & Wagner 2023; Ye et al. 2023; Yidana, et al. 2023). Lecturer preparedness and readiness are also affecting technology integration in universities (Dudhat 2023; Timotheou et al. 2023; Wongwatkit et al. 2023; Yidana, et al. 2023).

Opportunities in technology integration are identified to benefit 21st-century skills for greater collaboration and communication, and for improving digital literacy (Wu et al. 2023). Several authors mentioned personalised and enhanced learning experiences and expanded diversity in learning opportunities as opportunities for technology integration (Banafaa et al. 2023; Alenezi et al. 2013; Thu et al. 2023).

3.3 Recommendations for improving technology integration in STEM education

Frameworks are proposed for improving technology integration in STEM education (Diaz-Mendez et al. 2019; Mpofu 2019; Ramnarain & Ndlovu 2023). The framework includes six elements: learning goals, learning tasks, technologies, pedagogical practices, lecturer roles, and assessment. The studies also highlight the importance of alignment between these elements and the need for a whole-university approach to technology integration. Mukamba & Makamure (2020); Ma'rifah & Sinaga (2023) suggest full engagement of technology in teaching and learning to improve technology integration. Additionally, to improve technology integration lecturer professional development should be imparted with the necessary skills and expertise in its usage (Ayebi-Arthur et al. 2023; Toma 2023).

3.4 Implications for policy and practice in STEM education

This study reviews the policy landscape for STEM education in a number of countries, globally, regionally,

and locally. Technology integration policy is articulated well in South Africa and specified in other African countries (Ramnarain & Ndlovu 2023). The Zimbabwean curriculum has policies attached however during interviews with the higher education lecturers they mentioned that the policies are not well defined. Additionally, common themes should be identified in STEM education policy, such as the need to improve students' 21st-century skills, the need to engage students in STEM, and the need to prepare students for the future workforce. Furthermore, the importance of aligning policy with practice and ensuring that policy is implemented in a coherent and consistent manner should be highlighted.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Approach and Design

The study used a qualitative approach, a case of a university with 7 faculties.

4.2 Population

The population consists of lecturers, technicians, and students in a university with 7 faculties.

4.3 Sample

Two lecturers from each faculty were selected. Focus group from each faculty had five students and one technician was sampled from each faculty.

4.4 Instrument

Interviews and focus group discussions were used to collect data from the lecturers, technicians, and students respectively.

4.5 Data collection

Data was collected from the lecturers and technicians through one-on-one interviews. Then from students data was collected through focus group discussions. Coding of respondents was coded as follows: 14 Lecturers (L1–L14), Technicians (Tech 1–Tech 7), and students in Focus groups (Fgroup 1–Fgroup 7).

4.6 Data analysis and presentation

The data was analysed and presented thematically by the lecturers, technicians, and students in focus groups.

4.7 Ethical consideration

The researcher sought consent from the university under study and from the respondents to carry out the study. The research promised that the information from the respondents will be kept safe and private

5. RESULTS

The results of this study are based on the results of the interviews and the focus group discussions. Findings from L1, L4, L5, L7, L8; Fgroup 1–7 and Tech1, 3, 4, 7 indicated that technology integration had a positive impact on 21st-century skills, increased student engagement, and skills and knowledge were created. All the Fgroup 1-7 students reported that they had gained skills in problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, and digital literacy. The interviews with L1, L2, L4, L6, L7, L8, L9, L11, L12, and L13 revealed that the use of technology also helped to improve collaboration and communication.

However, there were also challenges mentioned by Tech 1–Tech 7 and L2, L3, L4, L7, L8, L9, L12, L14, and Fgroup 1–7 such as a lack of access to technology and a lack of training for students and lecturers in technology integration. Students also felt that blended learning is still significant to their learning for engagement and motivation purposes. Lecturers also mentioned their lack of preparedness as another challenge in technology integration. Additionally, all the technicians indicated infrastructure challenges (poor internet connectivity, power outages, and lack of digital literacy by students and some lecturers. Above all lecturers and focus groups indicated opportunities for technology integration as enhanced personalised learning; improved communication, and collaborations globally, regionally, and locally.

Fgroups highlighted that they need introductory foundations on how to integrate certain technologies into their learning. Lecturers and technicians recommended the need to improve lecturer professional development and to propose an institutional technology framework that is clear to all stakeholders. The institutional technology framework should involve all the necessary stages so that it can be reviewed to suit

the evolving technology. Professional development can be improved by organizing workshops, seminars, or short courses related to technology integration for the lecturers.

On implications for policy and practice in STEM education, the lecturers and technicians were not sure as they highlighted that they are not well versed with the policy as it is not clear to them.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study has found that technology integration during the COVID-19 pandemic has had a positive impact on STEM students' 21st-century skills, student engagement, and knowledge creation. However, there are still challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that all students have equal access to technology and the opportunity to develop their skills. Challenges of infrastructure, slim access to resources, and lack of lecturer preparedness are noticed. Besides challenges, technology integration has some opportunities that include increased collaboration and communication, and personalised learning. There is also a need for an institutional framework on technology integration and to improve lecturer professional development. Technology integration policy should be spelled out in black and white. This study has added to the growing body of research on the impact of technology integration on student learning.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made for policy and practice: Increase investment in technology infrastructure, including devices, connectivity, and training for students and lecturers. Develop blended learning models that combine online and face-to-face instruction, and provide the necessary support for lecturers and students. Improve access to educational resources, including open educational resources, to ensure that all students have access to high-quality resources. Evaluate and monitor the implementation of technology integration initiatives to ensure that they are effective and meet the needs of students. The study recommends that future research should focus on how to overcome the challenges of distance learning and how to make the most of the opportunities.

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